
PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF TEACHERS FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING DELIVERY IN NIGERIA

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Abstract

Professional development of a teacher is important to teacher's and learner's knowledge update. Teachers need to personally develop themselves to be abreast of the global trends and developments. It was observed that some teachers are not updated with developments around them even the world of Artificial Intelligent (AI) and do not know where the world is tilting to. Teachers need to develop themselves to be able to deliver and impact new knowledge and idea into the learners; a certified teacher should have interaction with the learners always and to develop skills in them. As a whole teacher one need to have knowledge of everything around him and should be able to give right information when needed; that will help the learner and make the teacher effective in the field of teaching. The paper looked at areas that teachers should develop himself, qualities of effective teacher and way forward was also suggested such that supervising agents of education should allow the teachers to attend developmental training, government at all levels should have budget for training and retraining of teachers and ensure its implementation to the letter among others.

Keywords: Professional development, Teacher training, Effective teaching, Instructional delivery

Introduction

Professional development of teachers is of critical importance to the next generation in our country. A handful number of various researches have evidently shown the short and long term positive effect that professionally trained teachers have on the learner's development. Quality academic programmes depend on the teachers' effectiveness and delivery in the class (Hamer & Pianta 2020). To be effective, teachers must develop specialized knowledge, skill, and practice, this is to sustain the effectiveness of teaching as a profession and promoting continuous growth of high quality in service professional development (Borko, 2020)

A teacher is one who is certified to inculcate knowledge into the learners for the purpose of effecting changes in their attitude and be effective in the society. On the other hand, a teacher assumes different capacities as an educator, instructor, tutor, lecturer and professor. Teachers at all level of the educational system are very important in the overall development of any nation. (Anho 2020), teacher's education is the process which nurtures prospective teacher and skills in the form of continuous professional development. Teacher's education revolves around the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitude, behaviours and skills required in the performance of effective duties in the classroom, and in social gatherings.

Education is the right of every child, therefore no child should be denied of it for any reason. This goes in agreement with the assertion of the World Summit on the state of Global Education for All conference (EFA). Ajayi (2021) opined that Nigeria has pledge her commitment to this with the inauguration of the policy on education. Educational History is the educational knowledge given in an educational institution to learners to make them familiar with various educational concepts, ideas and types that are common in the educational industry. It also gives knowledge of the past in the present for future preparedness. Education start from the cradle through life experiences till the grave, Experts says learning is a continuous exercise and a veritable tool for life-long development.

The future of a nation's educational system, socio-economic and political wellbeing lies with the quality of education given to the learners because they are the future leaders. Education builds on a shaky foundation will surely crumble and affects lives when it is needed and in turns affects the nation. Teaching-learning should start in the early stage of learning. Learners go through a huge variety of learning stages during this time, making great steps and what they learn at young age offers an important foundation for their learning in later life. The learning processes start from home and then moved to school and at various point of learning the responsibility lies upon the parents and teachers.

Barrister Kenneth Gbagi a former minister of state for education once said that the subscribers (education stakeholders) had been besieged with some challenges which include lack of basic infrastructure, uniform standards, segregated data, funds and dearth of qualified teachers. The policy is linking to the development of education centers on the existing public schools and the need to accommodate professional teachers' .The problem that have always reared its ugly head in the society is the issue of having adequate and professional hands that can teach at all level. This is the reason that necessitated this study

Concept of Professional Development for Teachers

Professional development as a concept is referred to as the development of a person in his or her professional roles. Teacher development is the professional growth a teacher achieves as

a result of gaining increased experience and examines his or her teaching skills. Gaththo (2020). Professional development includes formal such as (attending workshops, professional meetings, conferences and seminars) and informal experience such as reading academic discipline documentaries, professional publications, watching television documentaries. Ganser (2020).

A teacher is conceived as a reflective practitioner, someone who enters the profession with certain knowledge base and who will acquire knowledge and experience based on the prior knowledge. In so doing, the role of professional development is to aid teacher in building new pedagogical theories and help them develop their expertise in the field. There are two main phases of professional development; initial preparation and continuing development. Initial teacher training may also be available to serving unqualified teachers through distance education, out of school programme during vacation or on release from school for extended period of time. The professional competence of initial teacher training programme can be either conservative or concurrent with academic subjects.

Continuing professional development of a teacher comes from various source and agencies and in various forms; orientating teachers to upgrade qualification level join professional teachers associations in developing subjects teaching (e.g. Science Teachers Association of Nigeria STAN) or Teachers Union or school based improvement initiatives etc. Continuing professional development may be regarded as all forms of the in service, continuing education; on-the-job training; workshop etc. Mohammed (2021)

Teacher Approach to Professional Development

Development of a learner is a widely accepted principle in the field of education (Copple 2010). It stresses promoting all areas of learner development, cognitive, language, physical and social. It also calls for attention to the inter-relationship among these areas of development. It further specifies learning goals for the young learner. The whole teacher approach targets multiple dimension of the teacher development that includes knowledge and skill, attitude and classroom practices. All these variables play an equally important role in the teaching professional development. The focus on multiple dimensions offers teacher multiple pathways to learning and success. The whole teacher approach is also integrated. It was based on the premise that teacher attitudes, skills and practices interact and influence each other. The dynamics of this interrelationship provide a basis for facilitating teacher development rather than working to achieve isolated goals, the approach uses instructional strategies that build on the interrelationship among goals example of such is the building teacher's confidence that contributes to teacher's readiness to develop skills and motivate the implementation of new practices (Vartuli 2019). On the other hands, successful implementation of new practices increases a teacher sense of efficiency and suggests specific need for further knowledge and skill development (Berk 2019)

Though specific attitude, skills, and practices vary by domain, the principle of promoting multi-dimensional development by targeting these variables is applied to all domains of expertise. Deliberate integration of goal areas and instructional strategies maximize the rate of teacher progress. Developmental perspective is another distinct future of the whole teacher approach. This feature builds upon previous research on the developmental stages of teacher. It argues that for professional development to be effective, objective must correspond to different level of expertise in particular teaching domain such as mathematic, technology and literature. Berliner (2022). The approach facilitates the full range of teacher development, supporting growth from novice to expert level of proficiency. Working on different

developmental levels, the same professional development experiences are not appropriate for all teachers. To be appropriate, experience must be matched to the level, needs and interest of teachers. To illustrate the needs to match teachers development level it is good to consider what is appropriate for novice and for more advanced teacher in the area of learning.

Qualities of Effective Teachers

The whole teacher approach to professional development when properly implemented brings out the positive quality in the teacher that prepares himself for 21st century classroom. Teacher behaviours determine that effectiveness in the classroom and ultimately the impact they have on the learner's achievement.

Monitoring of Students

Effective teacher should have knowledge of every learner in the class and monitor their progress and how they are doing in the class. He is to use variety of measures to monitor their mastery and skill; he is to provide solution to any difficult situation the learner might find himself, he is also to document the records of the learner to see how they are learning. An effective teacher is to instill in student the potentials needed for the learner to move forward also make sure the potential is sustained. He should invite parents and guests to special class events, maintains unity in the class, he should use clear and language as means of instruction to give assignments and homework

Teacher as a Person

How the teacher relates with the learner has an impact on their experience in the class. Feelings may be transferred on the learners; the teacher personality is one of the first set of characteristics to look for in an effective teacher. An effective teacher assumes the ownership of the classroom and the learner's success; he uses his personal experience as example in teaching, he understands the feelings and emotion of the learner, communicate clearly, admits mistakes and correct them immediately, think and reflect on daily practices dress appropriately, listen attentively to the learners requests and responds with respect even in difficult times speak in appropriate tone and volume, work actively with the learners.

Giving Instructions

Effective teaching combines the need of good classroom management, teacher character, organization of classroom, effective planning and some other elements. The presentation of teaching materials to the learners and the use of previous experiences for the students to make authentic connection to the material are vital. The teacher uses the opportunity to bring out the best in the learners. Effective teacher uses student question to guide the lesson, use the pre assessment to guide instruction, develop element of an effective lesson, he uses established routine to capture more class-time, incorporate higher order thinking strategies, uses a varieties of activities and strategies to engage students, monitor students engagement in all activities and strategies with high number of students actively engaged in the class continuously, adjust the delivery and pacing of the lesson in response to students cues, effectively uses the entire classroom by walking round the classroom uses student centered classroom rather than teacher centered classroom, provides feedback either verbal, written or non-written design and bases assignment on objectivity and also assist students in planning for homework.

Classroom Management and Organization

The classroom management and style is known by its user. The teacher as the main user of the room determines the organization of the classroom and students. An effective teacher positions chair and table strategically that it will allow for interaction and other classroom activities. Effective teacher also maintain a physical environment with instructional materials and facilities are in good shape, walls are designed with pupil's artworks and pupils made crafts and designed to beautify the classroom. Students should also be encouraged to address one another in positive and respective manner, encourage interaction and allow good conversation about activities or tasks; manage emergency situation, maintain acceptable personal workspace.

Planning and Organizing Instructions

Effective teacher plan how to incorporate objectives from home or after school work. However teacher plan and organize instruction, the evidence of effective teacher can be seen in the classroom and by viewing the daily lesson objectives and activities, an effective teacher can be easily understood. Thus an effective teacher writes less, and plan for the every school day, students know the daily plan because an agenda of objectives and activities is given, students assessment and diagnostic data are available, students work samples are also available and considered when writing lesson plans. Lesson plans should be made to align with curriculum guide, stated learning objectives are incorporated into lesson plan, lesson plans should include accommodation of students with special needs, passing information and lesson.

Implementing Instructions

Effective teacher combines the essence of good classroom management, organization, effective planning and teacher's personal characteristic. The presentation of materials to the students and provision of experience for the students to make authentic connections to the material are vital. Effective teacher facilitates the classroom like a symphony conductor who brings out the best performance from each musician to make a beautiful sound. Implementing instructions is like opening a curtain in the theater where all the behind scenes, cast and crews works are hidden. Effective teacher uses student's questions to guide the lesson, uses pre-assessment to guide instructions to develop element of an effective lesson, uses established routine to capture more class time.

Challenges of Professional Teachers

It is necessary to look at the challenges of professional teacher to find necessary assistance / help for them.

In the developed countries of the world, quality assurance system will be put in place so as to set a target for the teacher to meet the standard and so the professional development is enhanced. In countries like UK & U S A, teachers were to be assessed by their performance with a view to identify teacher that may have left the profession. There is no mechanism to assess the teacher professional development in Nigeria and so professional development programme are not directed at appropriate audience

The ability of Teacher Registration Council of Nigeria (TRCN) to regulate entrance into the teaching profession is a short coming in the teaching professional development in Nigeria. Anyone can seek to be employed as a teacher without teaching skills; this is usually

common in private schools where proprietors want to maximize profits by employing anyone to teach without qualified certificates, they employ even school certificate or secondary school dropout. This discourages people willing to be member of the profession and so the profession becomes open to frustrated individuals who are unable to get other means of livelihood.

Inability of government to implement the UNESCO convention on the earn mark of 25% of country's budget allocation to education has impacted on teacher professional development and indeed educators as a whole.

High cost of educational materials, equipment's, books computer and other learning facilities hampers the professional development of teachers. A certified teacher with a meager take home (salary) will not be able to equip himself with modern educational gadgets that will be able to surf the internet to have up to date information

Poor conditions of service for teachers have also pose a big treat to the professional development of teachers. It leads to mass exodus of best brains from the teaching profession as a result of poor emolument. Teachers are to be specially paid with handsome salary package because they are the epitome of economic, socio-political and intellectual development of a nation.

Teacher Development Way Forward

Professional development of the teacher should be a continuous programme that would bring innovations, creativities and solve various educational issues.

This can be achieved through:

Development of ICT skills: teachers should be more compliance with world through their computer /ICT development skill which is a required for the effective competence in ICT education Application of ICT knowledge will allow the teachers to be abreast of various developments across the globe and join the global competition for the information. ICT could also be used to facilitate teaching learning activities. Development in ICT was recognize by European Commission in 2003 as first professional development .It is good for teachers to be grounded in the use of ICT.

Government at all levels from local government to federal should have budgets for training and re-training of teachers on their payroll for knowledge update.

Supervising arm of education should allow teachers to go for various professional development courses to help the learner's knowledge and to equip the teachers for the future at the same time

Professional teacher's development should be created to enable teacher handle their learners to be interested in learning and have critical thinking.

Conclusion

Quality education is determined by the teachers, they constitute major drive in the production of education activities. If they are wrongly informed, lazy, uninspired and uncommitted they become dangerous to the system by imparting wrong knowledge into the learners. Teachers are to help learners to adjust and adapt to the academic system through transition. Teachers help in the development of the brain and laid solid foundations for social

skills, self-esteem, and perception of the world and moral outlook as well as cognitive skill of the learner. As a result of all these important foundations, it is imperative that teachers must be adequately prepared/ developed to function effectively in the classroom. Based on these issues, this paper is advocating for spontaneous development of teachers in the teaching profession that will equip the teachers to stand firm against all global challenges.

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